

The Reality Of The Teaching Performance Of Physical Education And Sports Teachers In Light Of The Available Times For The Lesson From The Students' Point Of View

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Abstract

The research aims to try to diagnose the teaching performance of teachers of physical education and sports and to identify the extent of their application of new methods and methods in the physical education lesson, and the descriptive approach was used to observe and evaluate the course of the educational course of the subject of physical education and sports in light of the available times for the study of physical education compared to competencies (on a sample of 35 students in high school).

Where they were chosen by the intentional method, by viewing the behavior of one student during the lesson, provided that he is a male, normal height, and weight appropriate to his height and age, and this is according to the requirements of the form. Information, giving information, changing the location, and other behaviors). The most important results of the research, after appropriate treatment, indicated that the largest time the student spends in physical education and sports is on motor performance, waiting, and actual and academic learning.

The results also revealed small percentages of lost time that the student spends waiting, changing location, and performing other behaviors unrelated to the lesson. Through the results of the study, the study concluded that the professor of physical education and sports gives students enough time to invest it in what will benefit them in achieving their educational goals, and thus developing their skill capabilities and building their effective and balanced personality. Physical education and sports at the secondary stage is to control the course of the course by providing ready information to students, as well as in the planning process, the interest of the physical education and sports teacher in the evaluation process during and after the lesson, for the professor to have the ability to evaluate his teaching method.

Introduction

Among the areas covered by the teaching is the field of physical education and sports, which is similar to the rest of the fields and other educational materials because of its practical role in developing and crystallizing the personality of the individual from all aspects of movement, including psychological and social, and this depends on the movement activity that distinguishes him and which takes his group of physical and sports activities as a cultural and social support Where it gives the learner a healthy balance that guarantees him a healthy balance in all aspects and coexist in harmony with the external environment from the source of virtuous behaviors that give him the opportunity to actually integrate, and despite all this, he often harms them while practicing sports activities as a game and entertainment or a waste of time. One of the most important elements of the physical education lesson of the curriculum, its objectives, contents, methods and teaching methods, we find that counting evaluation is an important part of any educational or educational process. As it is issued to judge how to achieve the desired goals, and includes the evaluation of the first grade lesson time, curricula, teaching methods and teaching aids used and strengthening the performance of the teacher during his studies of physical education and sports and the floor for me. It is the method of serving the teacher and the learner as well, as it provides the first with the necessary information and reveals it to know the extent to which the set goals are achieved, and it allows the second to determine its position on the scale. (1)

Research problem

- Do the teachers give sufficient time for the student to perform the movement in the physical education and sports lesson?
- Do students invest the time he studied physical education and sports in the manner appropriate ,including back them to achieve the objectives of?

Research objectives

The research aims to achieve the following

- Knowing the adequacy of time that the professor gives to the student in motor performance.
- Knowing the extent to which students invest time in physical education and sports to achieve their goals.
- Knowing the extent of the physical education teacher's contribution to improving the performance of the physical education and sports lesson in secondary development.
- Knowing the methods and methods used and the means used during the implementation of the physical education and sports lesson and their compatibility with the dictates of the available times for the physical education lesson.
- Try to find the educational nature of khat between the generation of Sultalm on the one hand, and the educated among them, on the other hand, in terms of giving, receiving, teachers, knowledge and exchange.
- Attempting to design a notes card as a tool to collect information and evidence about student activity during physical education, mathematics and how to teach teachers.
- The extent to which educational recognition is applied according to the time and capabilities available in the studied physical education in educational institutions.

Research hypotheses

- Physical education and sports professors at the secondary stage embody teaching according to the available times and capabilities.
- Professors give students sufficient time to perform their movement during the physical education and sports lesson.
- Students invest time in physical education and sports in the appropriate manner in order to achieve their goals.

Research areas

- The human field :The study was conducted on a sample of 35 students from some schools at the secondary level ,distributed between intermediate and middle school.
- Time domain :The theoretical study was conducted: from the beginning of the corresponding academic year 2020/29/11To 2/18/2021

Spatial domain: The field study was conducted at the level of some secondary schools in Babel Governorate.

Research methodology and field procedures

Research Methodology

The researcher used the descriptive approach as it relates to the nature of the research.

The sample and how to choose it: The research community identified students from the sixth preparatory stage at Al Zalpmn School in Babel Governorate for the season 2020-2021, 93 students in the school were chosen a random sample of 35 students, with a visual amount of 37.634%. Social communication.

Search tools

The researcher used the following tools to collect data

Anderson Review and Appraisal Form:

Observation takes place during the physical education and sports lesson that the teacher meets for one student, and his height is normal, and his weight is appropriate for his height and age, and he chooses a target for viewing so that he can watch it. The movements and behavior do not have any kind of pretense and representation, and this system (the model time system (for student activity) was used in order to collect the information needed by the researcher on how to teach teachers, and this system was invented by Anderson and Sherman (1980) which contains fields for m attest and record Activities of one student during a tutor's lesson.

Below is a presentation of all the terms included in the Anderson View template

1. Motor performance: It is the sum of the repetitions a student spends in studying physical education and sports, and it is an intervention that includes games and skills training.
2. Receiving information: It is a repetitive group spent by the student in physical education and sports, which includes listening to your mother's teachers, other students in the lesson, viewing models and explanatory aids, awareness or visual or written explanations
3. Giving information: It is the total number of times a student spends studying physical education and sports, which includes exchanging information with teachers or with the students 'aim in a subject.
4. Waiting: it is the sum of the repetitions that the student spends without knowing, for example: waiting for the turn of play - waiting for the start of play - waiting for the beginning of the lesson.
5. Change of location: it is the total number of iterations that students spend in changing situations during the lesson without assigning (outside the scope of the lesson)
6. Other behaviors: It is the sum of the repetitions that the student spends in performing behaviors or movements that have nothing to do with the lesson or have nothing to do with it.

The form seen Anderson divided into six fields to diagnose behavior horizontally, as well as divided into eight stages to watch every stage broadcast of Ath - minute break and then followed by w not w minutes to watch and

so on until the end of the eighth stage, the viewer to monitor student behavior for five seconds and puts p not Meh in the corresponding field of behavior that the person in the case of more than the behavior of a watching one Visgel behavior longer for so and to do as we will have twelve watch every minute , six wth not thon watch at every stage of formed phases from XP do not w minutes, after recording the types of behavior gathered all views for each field separately and then combine the number of repetitions in each field, and in the case of a m not moments are recorded in the box pain is not moments for each stage:

1. The time of academic participation in motor learning: It is the sum of the time value that the student spends in studying the subject of physical education and sport, which includes the collection of the time value of movement performance plus the time of receiving the information in addition to the time of giving the information.
2. Time for direct participation in motor learning: It is the total value of the time the student spends in studying the subject of physical education and sports, where he is participating in kinetic education that makes physical movements that move an object or part of it, jumping, bouncing, rolling, etc.
3. Participation of time to others directly in the learning engine: it is the total value of time, and he is a common student in receiving information or giving information related to teaching movements or academic theoretical activities, and mathematical practice, such as answering questions, listening, reading laws, and audiovisualmeetings. Etc.
4. Lost Time: The total value of the time a student spends on the waiting list plus a change of location as well as other movements of the link to her lesson.
5. The percentage of direct and indirect participation time and wasted time: It is the division of the participation time percentage by the time of non-participation in the lesson activities, which is: (the time ratio of the time of performing the movement + the percentage of the time of receiving the information + the percentage of the time of giving the information (÷) the ratio of the waiting time + the percentage of time Location change + time ratio for other behaviors).
6. Percentage of direct and indirect participation time: is the division of the time percentage of the movement's performance by the time percentage of receiving information in addition to giving information, which is: (time percentage of movement performance (÷) the time percentage of receiving information + the time percentage of giving information)

Exploratory experience

Within this concept, the researcher conducted the exploratory experiment in a sample of (30) male and female students, and the aim of conducting the exploratory experiment was as follows: ((2))

1. Identify the difficulties and obstacles facing the researcher.
2. Identify the capabilities of the work team that help to accomplish its mission properly.
3. The extent of difficulties faced by the testers in the concept of scale instructions in terms of formulation and content.
4. The time taken to give instructions and to conduct a scale experiment. The time is calculated by extracting the average time resulting from dividing the sum of the times that the first and last testers spent by (2), which is equivalent to (20) minutes ($15 + 25/2 = 20$)

The main experiment: The researcher began applying the scale on the 35 members of the applied sample, representing students of the sixth preparatory stage in Al-Zahawi School for Boys.

Scale correction

The process of correcting one model took (3-4) minutes, and the scores of the testers ranged between (97-130) degrees with a mean (123,111) and a standard deviation (930), and on the assumption: (120)

Sixth: for the scientific foundations of scale

First: true internal harmony:

Correlation coefficient between paragraph score and overall score scale

The use of the validity of internal consistency between the paragraph of the university degree scale and after analyzing the statistically significant coefficients showed a correlation, all the fact that the value of (tt) calculated was greater than the scheduled amount (1.701), and at the degree of freedom (28) and the level of significance (0.05) ((3))

The correlation coefficient between the paragraph score and the total score of the field to which the paragraph belongs

To achieve this, the total sum of each of the five fields and the scores of the paragraphs to which they belong was calculated, and from it the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) was extracted between them and for the sample members whose number was (30) supervisors, and to know the type of statistical significance, the researcher used the equation (T) which showed an indication. The coefficients of all correlation because the computed value of (t) was greater than its table. With a value of (1.701), a degree of freedom (28), and a degree of significance (0.05)

Correlation coefficient between field scores and the scale sum

The researcher used the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) to extract the correlation coefficients between the field scores and the total degree of the scale, and to know the type of statistical significance, the researcher used the equation (tt) that showed the significance of all the correlation coefficients because the calculated value of (t) was greater than its tabular value. (1.701) with a degree of freedom (28) and a level of significance (0.05) ((4)).

Second: Stability

To verify the stability of the scale, the researcher used the half-segmentation method, so the scale paragraphs were divided into two halves, as the first half paragraphs included odd numbers, while the second section with even numbers and the two halves of homogeneity should be available at a good rate where the alpha value was extracted for them as the calculated (F) value (And when compared to the tabular value with a degree of freedom (34-34) and a significant level (0.05) of (1.854), it was found that it is not statistically significant, thus achieving homogeneity. After that, the researcher extracted the simple correlation coefficient (Pearson) between the sum of the two halves, which reached (0.777), which means the stability of half the scale, and in order to obtain complete stability, the equation was (Spearman and Brown). Applied as a value that has the stability factor (0.875) and to test its statistical significance, the researcher used the computed equation (tt) for (13.894), which was greater than its tabular value of (1.701) and with a degree of freedom. (28) and its level of importance (0.05), which is an indication of the stability of the high scale.

Statistical methods used: The researchers used the statistical bag (spss) for all statistical treatments

Presentation and analysis of results:

Presentation and analysis of the results of the question first:

The teachers give students ample time to make their move during a physical education and sports lesson.

Table No. (1) Shows the arithmetic mean, percentages and standard deviation

Standard deviation	Percentage	SMA	The sequence
45,18	45.06	130,50	Motor performance
13,79	9,75	30.04	Receive information
13,55	6,14	17,75	Give information
35,75	18,50	55,31	Wait
9,10	5.09	16,60	Location change
13,14	10,27	28,75	Other behaviors

It is evident from the above table that the percentages of times spent in each area of observation were different according to the frequency of the students' behavior observed during the lesson. As for the motor performance, the arithmetic mean of repetitions was (130.50) with a percentage (45.06) and the standard of deviation (45.18) The arithmetic mean of the frequency of the information receiving field was (30.04), the percentage (9.75) and the standard deviation (13.79), given the arithmetic mean of the information (17.75)) with a percentage (6.14) and a standard deviation (13.55) in the field. The arithmetic to wait for the repetition (55.31) as an estimated percentage (18.50) and a standard deviation (9.10) for the field of change. The site reached the arithmetic mean (16, 60) with a percentage (5.09) and a standard deviation of (9.10). A group of other behaviors not related to the lesson were also observed in the spectator students, where the arithmetic mean of the frequency of these behaviors was (28.75), and an estimated percentage (10) , 27) and with an evolution with Ari (13, 14)

Table (2) It displays the statistical description of the results of the teaching performance measure for physical education teachers

Indication type	Values sig	Values(t)Calculated	Hypothesis	standard deviation	SMA	Sample number	the scale
moral	0,000	6.982	120	9.30	123.11	35	Teaching performance

Table (2) shows scores on the teaching performance scale, where it reached an arithmetic center (123, 11), and the standard deviation (9.30), and when compared to the arithmetic mean temperature is the hypothesis of an alignment of the center (120), it shows that the arithmetic center Scale scores are greater than the middle hypothesis, and this means that Tatar mathematical teachers enjoy performing teaching, and for the purpose of standing up the importance of Sunday, aya. The differences between the Mediterranean, using the T-test for the first sample, the value of the error rate (CIJ amount (0.000) less (0.05), which indicates the presence of significant significance. ((5))

Discussion and interpretation of results

Discussion and interpretation of the results of the first question

Teachers give students ample time for motor performance during the studied physical education and sports. By reviewing the results of observations in the previous chapter and analyzing clearly, it was clear that the highest arithmetic average for the repeat behavior of the behavior record in the field of engine performance was estimated at 138.45, followed by the average of the arithmetic mean, your field. Wait. As for the arithmetic mean of the fields of receiving and giving information upon the reunification, the average of Evoan behaviors changed position, which was 17.59 as observed by observing the presence of other behaviors and movements that do not have any relevance to the lesson, as it reached the arithmetic average of these behaviors between Students and audience numbers do not do as much (26.72) as the time in which physical and mathematical education is studied should be used by the party's students in achieving their development and enhancing the skill, mobility, compatibility aspect, and the development of target competencies. To clarify these results, more percentages of times taken were added in each of the fields that were observed. He collected them all, and this confirms that there are large scholarships for students during the physical and sports educational lesson that are sufficient to be exploited in the performance of the motor, which could be from the activation of the educational process among students. He is not stupid and will not do what he is asked of if you are not enthusiastic and unrestrained in the work gives an atmosphere of atmosphere of any tax collector to the lesson and has the student interact with the exercises directed to him. Physical education and sports lesson depends on the circumstances and it may make the request always wait for its turn in performance, especially if there is a large number of students in the class and then it takes a large amount of lesson time in the waiting list, (6) and this was reflected in the registration of a good percentage in the waiting area reached (20.59%), where it came in second place after the percentage of motor performance. It is noted that all lesson time that teachers perform is spent on motor performance, giving and receiving of information. This benefits the student in all aspects, whether physical, cognitive, psychological or social. Speech overload, purposeful explanations of others, and other people's accurate explanations can be dispensed with during the lesson, especially when using demonstration methods, and this is noted by recording the percentage of time it takes a little to receive and give.

Discussion and interpretation of the results of the second question

Students invest the time they studied in physical education and sports in an appropriate way to return to them to achieve their goals. After presenting, displaying and extrapolating the results of the achievement fields, it became clear to us that the percentage of academic participation time is high, reaching 63.99%, which far exceeds the lost time estimated at 35.96%, which indicates that students invest much more than lesson time and it also affects the learning process positively, unlike time. The lost, which students spend waiting in changing the location and taking a position far from the physical lesson, (7) In this context, the physical and sports education of the teacher is essential in any school who is responsible for achieving the educational goals that students have acquired through their participation in both sports. Studied educational or in various activities. Returning to the time of direct participation and the direct participation of others, the percentage of the first time is higher than the percentage of the second time, meaning that students spend most of the lesson time in direct and effective participation in the performance of the engine and some time in the term of receiving and giving information and this is the end of the new method of teaching and the entrance to the competencies that are interested By the logic of learning through practice and presenting the student in the midst of the educational learning process and making it a center in which it impeded the development of his physical, skill, cognitive, psychological and social abilities. (8) In general, the appropriate investment for the time in which physical education and sports were studied by students and in achieving their educational goals, and is reflected in the organized and serious performance of the professor and his appropriate teaching methods and sense. Responsibility and honesty in work.

Conclusions and recommendations

1. Great time in view of motor performance has not prevented some teachers from resorting to making the performance of dynamic time in the introduction of some other planned activities in the educational curriculum.
2. The percentage of motor performance is high, which reflects the students' tendencies, motivation and love for movement activity, which leads to exploding their energies and highlighting their abilities.
3. The time when physical education and sports are studied when the exploitation of the mind is used and regulated in the performance of movement and academic learning by students, thus embodying the high-ranking professor and ruling him well in the stages of the lesson in all stages.
4. The decrease in the percentage of learning for time is a direct matter and a waste of time, but it is justified by literacy for the master of his article from all sides, both in terms of planning, good implementation, evaluation and the method of using the means of education.
5. Weakness of the means used in studying physical education and weak abilities

Recommendations

1. In educating teachers in secondary physical and sports that control the formulation of the competency index as well as in the planning process.

2. The interest of the physical education and sports teacher in the evaluation process during and after the lesson.
3. That the professor has the ability to evaluate his teaching method by participating in competitions held in sports activities.
4. Conducting similar studies at all educational levels.

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